

PERSONALITY TRAITS AND PSYCHOSOCIAL ADJUSTMENT OF STUDENTS WITH ACQUIRED PHYSICAL DISABILITIES IN IMO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT: The relevance of psychosocial adjustment in ensuring the overall wellbeing of students with acquired disability led to investigation of the relationship between personality traits of students with acquired physical disability and their psychosocial adjustment. A correlation research design was used for the study, as well as five research questions raised and five hypotheses formulated. The population for the study consisted of all secondary students with physical disabilities in the 70 public secondary schools in Owerri Education Zone 1 from which a total of 79 students were sampled purposively for the study. The instruments for data collection were researcher-made and titled “Personality Traits Scale” (PTS) and “Psychosocial Adjustment Scale” (PAS) which were face and content validated by specialists in Educational Psychology and Measurement and Evaluation. To test its reliability, Cronbach Alpha statistics was used to test its internal consistencies which yielded a value of .77 for PTS and .76 for PAS. The data obtained were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested using p-val at .05 level of significance. The result obtained showed that openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, all have a positive significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability while neuroticism has a negative significant relationship with psychosocial adjustment. Based on the findings, it was recommended that teachers should assign collaborative tasks to students in order to encourage social interaction between disabled and non-disabled students.

INTRODUCTION

Disability remains one of the significant challenges facing the human population. It is a state of incapacitation caused by non-functioning or absence of crucial parts of the human body due to damage. While some

damages that result in disability occur before birth – congenital disability, some occur after birth – acquired disability. Congenital disability is an impairment that a person is born with; it occurs during the uterine life and can be

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attributed to events (environmental and genetic) that occur during pregnancy which causes deformity at birth. Acquired disability, from its name “acquired” refers to a condition of impairment that occurs after a person has been born healthy and functional. It then results from happenings in the postnatal environment such as accidents, illness, or exposure to harmful chemicals that impair certain bodily or sensory functions. The Federal Ministry of Education as cited in Adiela (2023) classified disabilities into the following impairments: Visual (blind and partially sighted), hearing (deaf and partially hearing), physical and health, intellectual disability, speech and language, learning disabilities (psychological, neurological phobia or challenges), multiple disabilities, gifted and talented, and albinos. However, this research concentrates on physical disability specifically acquired physical disability.

Physical disability is an impairment that affects bodily movement. This kind of disability is associated with the hands, legs and spine which makes some motor skills nearly impossible. Identifying people with this condition is not difficult due to their obvious impairment of mobility as well as their constant use of movement aids such as wheel chairs, crutches and walking sticks among others. Though causes of physical disability can be congenital, it is most times acquired through unfortunate events such as accidents and illness that lead to immobility or in extreme cases – amputation which leads to use of prosthetics.

Regardless of the nature, cause, or dimension of disability, there is need for adjustment. This provides a way for the individual to come to terms with their condition and as well fit in an

environment alien to their condition. In the social environment, psychosocial adjustment is crucial; it relates to emotional response towards a new development or environment which influences the individual’s relationship with other persons. In the words of Odofin and Ebenuwa-Okoh (2023) “it is the interpersonal interactions and relations which influence individual’s development and behaviour” (p. 176). In psychosocial adjustment, emotion remains integral. Much of a person’s behaviour is based on and directed by their emotion. For the disabled, their feelings towards their condition with respect to their environment determine how they would react to it; but for a person with acquired disability, this goes beyond that. Having experienced what it feels to be completely functional in physical activities, they must first come to terms with their condition before their environment is put into play. The need to first adjust to their new condition may be as overwhelming as adjusting to their social life. When the individual must have become well-adjusted in their condition through provision of mobility aids, and other medical assistance required, then comes the need to adjust to their environment. People’s basic adjustment problems are not necessarily different irrespective of disability, however, disability poses a considerable burden that leads to adjustment problems (Jijimolv, Sneejith, Sreehari, & Joseph 2014).

Social interaction is a crucial aspect of living and also one of the criteria for assessing development in psychology. It is also used in determining one’s ability to regulate one’s emotions which is necessary in relating with people in different vicinities. The social interaction with people

outside one's intimate environment (such as the home) requires adjustment because of the peculiarities associated with different environments. Pertaining to students, adjusting to the school environment is a precursor to achieving their academic goals. The school environment takes into consideration academic and non-academic activities, and for the physically disabled student, includes the school building. The later – school building is considered because the school may have been designed and built without considering the disabled, although inclusive education has been put in place by the Federal Government of Nigeria (FRN). For successful adjustment in the school environment, the disabled student has to first surpass the hurdles posed by the structure of the school with or without the assistance of other students. This might cause a serious strain on the disabled student's psychosocial adjustment especially when the disabled relies on other students for aid, such as climbing a flight of stairs or wheeling the chair. Such situation will not only attract attention to the student's condition but will make other students become weary of the disabled and likewise avoid them.

In social interaction, the disabled student due to their condition, may not participate in some activities in the school even when they aspire to. This obviously makes them feel left out and discriminated based on their condition; therefore there tend to be a limited social interaction between the disabled student and other students. Sometimes students avoid much interaction with the disabled due to their disfigured body (in cases of amputation), or the disabled students themselves shy away from

other students due to feeling of inferiority. The disparity in social interaction may very much affect learning and subsequently the academic performance of the disabled student. The importance of social interaction in learning is ascertained in a study by Yedemie and Yidegi (2021) which showed a significant positive relationship between academic social interaction and academic achievement. This proves that social interaction does not only build and ensure positive relationship between students, but prepares the emotional environment for learning to take place.

The limitations caused by disability becomes more psychologically disrupting when it is an acquired disability. The student's newly developed impairment has caused a constraint in almost all their daily activities in ways they never experienced. How the student perceives and accepts such development influence how they respond to it. While some students may very well adjust to life and their environment, not minding their disability and are able to cope and interact well with other people, others may not be well adjusted. The importance of psychosocial adjustment in such challenging life situation gave rise to the need to investigate variables that may influence it such as personality traits.

Personality is a term that best describes a person's peculiar characteristics which influence their way of life and as well distinguish them from other persons. It refers to the organization and coordination of an individual's overall behaviour when they interact with their environment (Odojin and Ebebuwa-Okoh 2023). Personality traits according to the definition by Soto, Kronayer and Liang (2016) is the stable characteristics of an individual in

aspects of cognition, affect or behaviour which is consistent across relevant situation. Trait provides a classification system for understanding people and their behaviour (Chell, 2007), and according to Bello (2024) personality traits involve emotional regulation, temperament, and self-regulation which is fundamental to social interaction and management of stress. An important feature of personality traits is that they are not distinct but reflect continuous distributions, which is why introverts and extraverts are not two distinct types of people but who score relatively high or low along a continuous distribution (Cummings & Sanders, 2019); this shows that personality is not static but varies depending on the individual. This opposes the notion of a person being constrained to a particular personality and therefore one who is highly introvert or scores medium in introversion may score low on extraversion and not nil.

The five-factor model which includes five broad trait is the most widely used system of personality traits. The broad five traits are: openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism with attributes peculiar to them. Openness to experience is a personality trait that represents an individual's willingness to explore and experiences new dimensions of things. They are generally curious, imaginative and creative. This makes them able to accommodate and tolerate new and unusual ideologies. According to Bucker, Maes, Denissen and Sluchmann (2020) people who score high in openness to experience are less likely to feel lonely. Conscientiousness describes the meticulous kind of people who pay close attention to details and are extremely

careful in performing their tasks and therefore takes their obligations seriously. Study by O'Brien and DeLongis as cited in Bartley and Roesch (2011) found that people who are higher in conscientiousness use more coping strategies which appear effective in situations the person can control. Extraversion tends to be manifested in outgoing talkative, energetic behaviour (Thompson, 2008). Agreeableness refers to personality trait that describes individuals who are considerate about other people and tend to cooperate with others to ensure harmonious relationship. Neuroticism is a personality trait that is governed by negative emotions and therefore easily exhibit fear, and anxiety, and depression; therefore they are more vulnerable to harm and less likely to deal with stress.

In dealing with acquired disability, personality traits affect the students' psychosocial adjustment. A student's characteristic pattern of behaviour very much influence their ability to emotionally and socially adjust to their environment in the face of a disability; therefore personality trait could be the reason why some disabled students are very much interactive with other students, and engage in school activities very well, while some are secluded, cuddled up in a corner, always looking sad, and not associating with anyone. Different studies have investigated personality traits and its relationship with psychosocial adjustment such as Odofin and Eбенуwa-Okoh (2023) whose study discovered that the five personality traits jointly had a positive relationship with students' psychosocial adjustment, with male students having higher psychosocial adjustment than females. Grgurinovic and Butkovic (2023) study on personality trait and psychosocial adjustment

in patients with limb amputation, showed that personality traits – extraversion, agreeableness, and open-mindedness positively correlated with adjustment to limitation. Also Azic, Becivic and Jokovic (2010) study showed that personality trait – extraversion, openness to experience and conscientiousness have positive relationship with social adjustment. According to Anymene, Ejichukwu and Azuji (2019) research on extraversion, neuroticism, and openness to experience as predictors of students' social adjustment discovered that these three personality traits predicted students' social adjustment. Hayes and Joseph as cited in Anymene et al. (2019) study showed that extraversion was associated with social adjustment. Nagel and Anand (2012) revealed that personality traits like interpersonal affect and conformity assisted the process of adjustment while those like anxiety did not. According to the study by Cai, He, Wu and Jia (2023), neuroticism was negatively correlated with quality of life of people living with disability. In the study of Boyce and Wood (2011) on adaption to disability found that agreeable individuals adapt quickly and fully to disability. Psychosocial adjustment remains important in a person's ability to live harmoniously in their environment. It ensures a person's psychological wellbeing through adequate adjustment to the demands and changes in the environment they may find themselves. For the disabled, especially people living with acquired disability, its need becomes heightened. Through psychosocial adjustment the disabled is able to adjust to their condition in a way that allows them fit in any environment they might find themselves. Psychosocial adjustment requires them to be

emotionally and socially adjusted to their condition in order to be able to cope with their disability and as well engage in social interaction with others. A student living with disability would through their psychosocial adjustment become able to cope with schooling, which will very well enhance their academic performance. Due to the relevance of psychosocial adjustment in the face of physical disability – especially an acquired physical disability, the researcher is prompted to investigate the disabled personal characteristics such as their personality trait and its relationship with their psychosocial adjustment.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aims to investigate the relationship between personality traits and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired disability in Imo State, Nigeria.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The specific purpose of this study is to:

1. Determine the relationship between openness to experience and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability
2. Determine the relationship between conscientiousness and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability
3. Determine the relationship between extraversion and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability
4. Determine the relationship between agreeableness and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability
5. Determine the relationship between neuroticism and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability

RESEARCH JUSTIFICATION

The result of this study will be of great value to all stakeholders in education such as the government, parents, teachers, school administrators, students and researchers. The government had already insured that the disabled is not discriminated against, through the policy of inclusive education. This study however would alert them that inclusive education though a great step, does not completely assure the disabled of positive living – there is need for adjustment. The parents are the guardians of the children, and therefore are through this study, exposed to some factors that impact the adjustment of their disabled child. School administrators and teachers are through this study, enlightened on the problems disabled students face in the school environment; while the students themselves are made aware of impact of their personality on their psychosocial adjustment. This study serves as a basis and a resource material for further studies by other researchers in area of disabled students' adjustment.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were raised for the study

1. What is the relationship between openness to experience and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability?
2. What is the relationship between conscientiousness and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability?
3. What is the relationship between extraversion and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability?

4. What is the relationship between agreeableness and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability?
5. What is the relationship between neuroticism and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance

1. The relationship between openness to experience and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability is not statistically significant
2. The relationship between conscientiousness and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability is not statistically significant
3. The relationship between extraversion and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability is not statistically significant
4. The relationship between agreeableness and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability is not statistically significant
5. The relationship between neuroticism and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability is not statistically significant

METHOD

Research Design

The study was conducted using the correlation research design. The correlation research design was utilized because it establishes the relationship between two variables (Independent and dependent), the direction of such relationship (positive or negative), and the magnitude (High, medium, low). This design

(correlation) was therefore crucial in determining the relationship between the personality traits of students with acquired physical disability and their psychosocial adjustment.

Population and Sample Size of the Study

The population of the study consisted all students (excluding JSS1 and SS3) with physical disabilities in 70 public secondary schools in Owerri Education Zone I. The zone is comprised of five Local Government Areas: Owerri-North, Owerri-West, Owerri-Municipal, Mbaitoli and Ikeduru. Purposive sampling technique was used to sample only students with acquired physical disabilities, which gave rise to 79 students as the sample size used in the study.

Research Instrument

The instrument used in the study was a researcher-made scale titled “Personality Traits Scale (PTS)” with 25-items and five clusters, and “Psychosocial Adjustment Scale (PAS)” with 15-items. Both instruments were rated using a four-point likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA) – 4

points, Agree (A) – 3 points, Disagree (D) – 2 points, and Strongly Disagree (SD) – 1 point. The instruments were face and content validated by specialists in Educational Psychology and Measurement and Evaluation. Before its administration, the reliability of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach Alpha to test its internal consistency; this yielded an alpha value of .77 for PTS and .76 for PAS which are reliable.

Administration

After the researcher was granted the permission to conduct the study in the sampled schools, the instruments were administered on the selected participants and collected by the researcher immediately they were rated. This ensured no copy was lost.

Method of Data Analysis

The data generated from the instruments were statistically analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested using p-val at .05 level of significance.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation between openness to experience and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired disability

Variables	N	Openness to experience	Psychosocial adjustment	P-val	Decision
Openness to experience	79	1	.72	.000	Significant
Psychosocial adjustment	79	.72	1		

Table 1 shows the relationship between openness to experience and psychosocial adjustments of students with acquired disability. A coefficient of .72 shows a high positive relationship between

the variables. P-val of .000 at .05 level of significance shows that the relationship is significant, therefore rejecting the null hypothesis. Individuals who score high in

openness to experience are creative and more likely to adapt to new conditions as they are capable of exploring new phenomenon. Rather than sulking, they employ their creativity in ways that can help them achieve goals despite limitations. Bucker et al. (2020) rightly posited that people who score high in openness to experience are less likely to feel lonely. The result from table 1 is in line with the result of

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation between conscientiousness and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired disability

Variables	N	Conscientiousness	Psychosocial adjustment	P-val	Decision
Conscientiousness	79	1	.68		
Psychosocial adjustment	79	.68	1	.000	Significant

Table 2 shows that conscientiousness positively correlated with psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability. The coefficient of .68 indicates a moderate positive relationship which is significant based on a p-val of .000 at .05 level of significance; therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. Conscientious individuals are highly engaging in activities and are very meticulous; therefore they are likely not be hindered by disabilities, but would seek a way to perform their tasks and actively engage in

Table 3: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation between extraversion and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired disability

Variables	N	Extraversion	Psychosocial adjustment	P-val	Decision
Extraversion	79	1	.70		
Psychosocial adjustment	79	.70	1	.000	Significant

Table 3 shows the correlation between extraversion and psychosocial adjustments of

Grgurinovic and Butkovic (2023) study which among findings, discovered that open-mindedness positively correlated with psychosocial adjustment of students with limb amputation. Also Azic et al. (2010) study showed that personality trait - openness to experience have positive relationship with social adjustment.

activities required of them through proper adjustment. Study by O’Brien and DeLongis as cited in Bartley and Roesch (2011) found that people who are higher in conscientiousness use more coping strategies which appear effective in situations the person can control. The findings in table 2 is in consonance with study by Azic et al (2010) study which showed that conscientiousness positively correlated with social adjustment.

students with acquired disability. A coefficient of .70 indicates that extraversion has a high

positive relationship with psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability. A p-val of .000 at .05 level of significance shows that the relationship is significant, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. Extraversions individuals are highly sociable individuals and therefore can easily adjust themselves into any environment. This means that in a case of physical disability, an extravert tends not be hindered by their condition. Their sociable nature makes them

able to relate with other people which therefore eases the stress that their condition may cause. The findings of this study relates a previous research by Hayes and Joseph as cited in Anyaeme et al. (2019) which indicated that extraversion correlates to social adjustment. According to Anyaeme, et al. (2019) students who are high in extraversion tend to engage socially with others, however contrary to the present study they were poorly adjusted.

Table 4: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation between agreeableness and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability

Variables	N	Agreeableness	Psychosocial adjustment	P-val	Decision
Agreeableness	79	1	.52		
Psychosocial adjustment	79	.52	1	.000	Significant

Table 4 indicates that agreeableness positively correlates with psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired physical disability. A .52 coefficient shows that the relationship is moderate, while p-val of .000 at .05 level of significance shows that the relationship between the variables is significant; this leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Agreeable individuals are able to positively correlate with

people and this can lead to their ability to proper adjust to their environment in the face of a disability. This result is in consonance with Boyce and Wood (2011) study who found that agreeable individuals adapt quickly and fully to disability. Also in the study by Grgurinovic and Butkovic (2023) which showed that agreeableness positively correlated with adjustment to limb amputation.

Table 5: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation between neuroticism and psychosocial adjustment of students with acquired disability

Variables	N	Neuroticism	Psychosocial adjustment	P-val	Decision
Neuroticism	79	1	-.60		
Psychosocial adjustment	79	-.60	1	.000	Significant

Table 5 shows the relationship between neuroticism and psychosocial adjustment of

students with acquired physical disability. Pearson coefficient “r” which is -.60 and a p-val

of .000 at .05 level of significance indicates a significant negative and moderate relationship between the variables. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. Neurotic individuals are associated with fear and anxiety. They are most times pessimistic about the future or other uncertain conditions which makes them to poorly adjust in an unfamiliar environment or

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The findings of this study provided the knowledge that individual characteristics of students with acquired physical disability such as their personality influences their psychosocial adjustment. The big-five model personality traits (openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism) were investigated which proved to positively correlate with students' psychosocial adjustment except neuroticism which negatively correlated with students' adjustment. This result is an indication that though adjustment of students with acquired physical disabilities depends on support from their environment, it also depends on their personality trait. Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations were made:

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condition such as disability. This result is in line with Nagel and Anand (2012) study which revealed that while personality traits like interpersonal affect and conformity assisted the process of adjustment, those like anxiety did not. Also according to the study by Cai, et al. (2023), neuroticism was negatively correlated with quality of life of people living with disability.

1. Teachers should assign collaborative tasks to students in order to encourage social interaction between disabled and non-disabled students which facilitates adjustment.
2. A school counsellor should be employed in school to help maladjusted students with disabilities to adjust properly.
3. Schools should be constructed with the needs of the disabled in mind; this includes making construction that enables wheelchairs to be rolled in, clutches, among others.
4. Stringent rules should be made in schools against the discrimination of the disabled in school environment.
5. The government should provide walking aids for disabled individuals that may not afford them.

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